
The roles of a teacher for Language Laboratory Sessions

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Abstract:

English is a language of opportunities that is prominent in securing desirable employment for graduates. Therefore, accuracy and fluency are essential in the use of the English language. In many professional graduate programs of Indian higher education, English communication skills subject has been introduced. A well-equipped, technology-based language lab has been set up for effective teaching. Laboratory classes (practical sessions) provide good opportunities to explore themselves. It requires a responsible teacher. The present research paper discusses the roles of a teacher like a leader, planner, instructor, executor, evaluator, facilitator, communicator, problem solver, motivator, diagnostician, educator, learning resource, demonstrator, advisor, innovator, involver, informer, much more of a language teacher during the practical sessions.

Keywords: Language laboratory, teacher, learner, communication skills, etc

Introduction:

English is a language of opportunities, and in the modern era, it plays a prominent role in securing desirable employment for any graduate. The world has become a global village; English is the connecting or linking language. In this respect, accuracy, and fluency are essential in the use of a language. A person desirous of working globally has English as the only means of communication. Therefore, communication skills subject has been introduced in many graduate programs in Indian higher education. For teaching communication skills effectively, the language lab is urgently needed. Laboratory classes provide students with a first-hand experience of communication skills with ethical concepts and the opportunity to explore ideas. The language lab intends to develop confidence among students for interactions and presentations in English, motivating them to practice language skills outside the classroom. Leading a laboratory session has challenges and opportunities that differ from those in a standard classroom environment. The prime purpose of the lab is to provide students with a platform to sharpen their English language skills. In this context, the role of a teacher who trains students with the help of a language lab is essential. The fluency in communication skills depends on the teacher.

This study aims at answering the questions.

1. Which roles does a language teacher perform to conduct successful language laboratory sessions?
2. Does a teacher's active role help the students develop their communication skills?

Thus, the study assumes that a teacher's active role helps students develop communication skills. He may boost the confidence among the students for the effective use of communication skills on any platform.

The rationale for the study:

Before the introduction of computers, especially before 1990, teachers used a tape-based system to develop the student's communication skills. The role of the teacher was different at that time. The listening activities were given the priorities in the teaching classroom. Now modern Technology with the help of computers has been introduced. A unique and dedicated lab with all the necessary amenities is used in every educational institute. There are many educational institutions in India. Many new English teachers are required to teach communication skills. To be an influential teacher, they should know the role of a teacher. The present paper will be important in this regard. Much research has been done on the utilization of language labs for the improvement of communication skills. Still, the role of a teacher who teaches communication skills with the help of a language lab is much more critical. Therefore, this paper is equally important.

Method:

For this research, the researcher used a quantitative method to collect information from books, papers published in journals, and blocks on websites. He also used the qualitative research method. He conducted informal interviews with the faculty members of Gaya College of Engineering. He also collected information from the English language teachers of various colleges in Bihar. Therefore, this research is a combination of quantitative as well as qualitative research methods.

Literature review:

Kabir Das, 15th-century Indian mystic poet and saint said

गुरुगोबिंददोनोखड़ेकाकेलागूपाय

बलिहारीगुरुआपनो, गोबिंददियोबताय

This means If I encounter God and Guru both on my way, I will first bow down to the Guru as he is the one who showed me where to look for God.

Buchanan and MacPhee (1928) and Bagster-Collins, (1930) express that from 1893, commercial record sets were available in Spanish and English as a foreign language. Still, the phonograph was only used in regular classes and for self-study at home. Later, it started with teaching mathematics, science, and foreign languages in American schools by 1958, but Derthick (1965) and Hocking (1967) first launched in 1957 and then in 1958 by military organizations. Later, Leon (1962), Peterson (1974) & Saettler (1990) state that the first lab was established at the University of Grenoble in 1908 (P. 187). Brink (1986), Church (1986), Hutchinson (1964), and Vanderplank (1985) agreed with Hayes 1963 that "the language laboratory works and produces better results than would be possible without it...[which].....probably does not need documentation" (as cited in Hocking, 1967, p.61). Otto (1989) pointed out, "a computer is a powerful tool for the language laboratory (p.39). Delcolque et al. (2000) add that the first audio device welcomed the phonograph and immediately adopted other advances in audio Technology, such as magnetic tape and digital media.

Parker (1962) defines the language laboratory as: "an area containing equipment designed to facilitate second/foreign language learning" (p.67). The Webster's New World College Dictionary defines a language laboratory as "a classroom in which students learning a foreign language can practice sound and word patterns individually or under supervision with audio equipment, etc.". Cesar (2006) defined a language laboratory as: "...a teaching tool requiring the implementation of well-constructed tasks based on the students 'needs'". Beder (2008), in defining a language laboratory, stated: "A Language Laboratory is a room in a school, college, training institute, university or academy

that contains special equipment to help students learn foreign languages by listening to tapes or CDs, watching videos, recording themselves. Etc.”

However, more than just a laboratory with all modern technology-based computer systems is required. A skillful teacher is also needed to achieve the expected outcome: communication skills. The National Policy of Education for India (1986) states, "The status of the teacher reflects the socio-cultural ethos of a society; it is said that no people can rise above the level of its teachers."

The role of teachers is to help students learn by imparting knowledge to them and setting up a situation in which students can and will learn effectively. The teacher's role is essential even in language lab while teaching communication skills to any graduate.

Role of Teacher in Language Lab:

- **Leader:**The quality of the language teacher is to be a good leader.They foster critical and creative thinking and support learners in a learning exercise. They are visionary, inspirational, self-aware, open-minded, and need patience. While conducting the session in the language lab, learners ask questions and need the proper support to whom they respond. They are always ready for new learning ventures and continuous improvement. Their leadership skills provide enthusiasm among the learners and get inspiration to learn communication skills.
- **Planner:**Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam said, "A good teacher, with meticulous planning, prepares himself for teaching and the student for acquiring knowledge." Planning is a systematic exercise of determining a future course of action by identifying objectives, needs, priorities, and existing/likely capacities, within a given timeframe. Planning is a roadmap to anyone's success. The language teacher is open to this proverb.

Whenever the teacher plans activities related to communication skills, he knows what he wants to achieve through that particular activity. At the same time, it becomes clear what the future might hold and what his goals are. Therefore, the role of the teacher who teaches communication skills and assigns activities in the language lab is a planner. Language lab session requires planning. There are many activities related to language development. The teacher is responsible for planning to introduce the required training to the students for the expected outcome.

Ex. In India, the engineering courses are for four years. After finishing the degree course, along with the technical knowledge, it is expected that the students to be master communication skills. Communication is a continuous teaching-learning process. It can be developed only by constant practice. Fourth-year students' requirements differ from first- or second-year students. If the teacher introduces the same activity to all the students, the aim will not be satisfied.

- **Preparator:**Maximum usage of the available infrastructure in the organization is the organization's first and most crucial motive. Therefore, in many institutes, a well-equipped lab assigns to more programs. In Gaya College of Engineering, Gaya in the language lab, MAT Lab software, and CAD CAM lab software has been installed, and some particular time has been assigned to MAT lab. CAD CAM lab and the concerned faculty members handle the lab. As many faculty members are using the same lab for different purposes, the possibilities is to misplacing things or raise a technical problem. Sometimes, due to improper handling, the headphones get damaged; therefore, many preparatory works are needed to execute the planned activities

in the language lab. Ex. The teacher has to check the availability of electricity and whether the server, computers, headphones, TV, language lab software or videos, etc., are working correctly.

- **Instructor:** While operating the lab, the learners need the proper instructions. The teacher gives instructions about the operation of the particular software, particularly assigned activities, headphones, mouse, keyboard handling, and many more. College students are young and naughty according to age and eager to experiment, so they need the proper instructions. As the teacher of communication skills is from a non-technical background, he has to depend on some technical person. It is only possible that the technical staff will be present sometimes in the language lab. Therefore, the role of a teacher as an instructor is more important.
- **Executor:** Execution of the planned activity properly is needed. It is well-known that just sitting in front of the computer, ideally listening to the activities for one hour or two hours, is not learning. There is an integration of different activities like listening skills followed by speaking skills. So that the learners do not get bored. The ratio of maximum learning is achieved. The teacher of communication skills can do this; therefore, the teacher plays the executor.
- **Evaluator:** The language teacher assigns the activity to the learner. They go through it. They listen carefully. Moreover, they declare that they have finished the training. The teacher has to check whether they completed the activity with proper understanding. The teacher has to conduct an evaluation activity so that he can find the performance level. Ex. The teacher performs the pronunciation activity to improve the pronunciation of the words. This activity consumes 12.00 Minutes.

After finishing this activity, the teacher calls every student onto the stage and asks 2 – 3 comments that they listen to. This activity helps the teacher to understand the student's progress. Therefore, the role of the language teacher is an Evaluator.

- **Facilitator:** The role of a teacher has been shifted from teacher to facilitator. The language teacher always facilitates the learners to involve in the assigned activity. The language lab session is mainly based on practice. The teacher conducts activities like self-introduction, unforgettable days of life, festivals, group discussion, presentation, situational conversations, etc. The learners are from various backgrounds, so they hesitate to participate in the activity. They have stage fear. In such cases, the role of a facilitator is essential. He provided some help to such students and tried to involve them in the activity and move them toward improving their communication and employability skills. Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan says, "The true teachers help us think for ourselves." Every student tries for their best thinking and practice and promotes mutual understanding. The students get support to do their best review from the teacher. The teacher is the only person who can introduce the student to the proper learning goal.
- **Communicator:** Effective communication skills are the most fantastic ornament of any person. The teacher is the creator of the nation. His communication skills create a mark on the personality of his learners. The teacher who handles the language lab needs good communication skills. The teacher has to interact with the learners on many occasions and communicate with them in understandable language. While conducting the language session in the lab, he has to instruct the learners on various stages. If he cannot train properly

and clearly in the target language, the learners will not be motivated to learn.

- **Problem solver:** The learners of the language face many problems. It becomes a habit if they are overcome after a particular time. Ex. Students need help with their speaking skills. They gather information on the assigned topic from the teacher. They use random vocabulary. They often ask the teacher about the appropriate word for appropriate expressions. The teacher helps them in such situations. Therefore, while introducing the activities, the language teacher plays the role of a problem solver, which is essential.
- **Motivator:** Teachers as a motivator provides stimulation and encouragement to increase students' interest and motivation. Interests are the awareness, desire, and attention of someone toward a particular object associated with them that is associated with strong feelings (Witherington, 1982; Syah, 2011; Ahmadi, 2003). Interest is a preference for an activity implemented through active participation (Slameto, 2010). Therefore, interest is vital to be enhanced because learning interest influences learning achievement (Djamarah, 2002). With motivation, learning is possible. For good learning, motivation is an essential factor; therefore, the teacher plays the role of a motivator. He motivates the students to listen or watch the assigned activities and use them in practical life according to the situation. Motivation stimulates students to learn, the teacher encourages them, and they get positive inspiration for learning.
- **Professional:** A language teacher always bears professional qualities. He maintains his attire, shoes, hairstyle, sheaving, way of communication, time management, etc. Ex. The teacher assigns the activity of reading skills. After finishing it, he asked questions based on the activity, and if the learner failed to respond correctly,

he asked the particular student to read again. This attitude makes the learner severe and the teacher a professional.

- **Ethical:** Maxwell and Schwimmer (2016: 259) note that ethical considerations accompany every aspect of a teacher's work. *Ethics* are interpreted as good and bad with commitment and moral duty. The language lab teacher conducts the activities without killing time. He completes his duty on time. He completes his assigned activities on time.
- **Supervisor:** The teacher supervises the teaching-learning activity. In the language lab, he supervises his students, the infrastructure provided to the lab, etc. During the session, he checks whether the learners are working on the assigned activity. Ex. If the teacher gives an activity for improving Listening skills, the teacher supervises whether the learner is seriously completing that activity. Even the teacher supervises whether all equipment is properly working.
- **Coordinator:** Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary defines a coordinator as "a person who organizes the different parts of an activity and the people involved in it so that it works well." The teacher is the coordinator for the language lab session. He takes the help of the technician. He asks the assistant to stay during the session. He forms groups of learners. He coordinates between the need of the learners and the study material available.
- **Diagnostician:** This is connected to the verb *diagnose*, which means '*to find out what problem someone has*'. The doctors often use the verb. ' '. Before advising or prescribing any medicines, the doctor thinks about the patient's problems. Similarly, the teacher carefully analyses their learner's communication skills and finds out what they can and cannot do. This helps the teacher to understand the needs of the students. The language teacher conducts the pretest in any form

whether oral or written, by keeping the record or not to see the level of the learner's communication skills. The teacher analyses the level and provides the activities accordingly. He creates three stages of his study materials – Basic, advanced, and professional.

- **Educator:** The teacher is responsible for teaching the language and developing the child's knowledge and social, emotional, and cognitive skills. The teacher teaches learning strategies, dictionary skills, inference skills, and many more, which contribute not just to language learning but also to the learner's overall cognitive abilities so that he becomes the master in his chosen field.
- **Learning resource:** The role of the teacher as a learning resource is essential. When the learner starts new learning, it is assumed that he may face a problem. He requires authentic learning resources to find the answers to the problem. In colleges, the teacher is the first learning resource for the students. He tries to find the solutions to his problems from the teacher. Ex. The learner needs to learn the importance of commas in writing. During the lab session on writing skills, the learner may ask his doubt. That time the teacher plays the role of learning resource.
- **Counselor:** According to Swami Vivekanand, “A true teacher can immediately come down to the level of the student and transfer his soul to the student's soul and see through and understand through his mind”. During the language lab sessions, the teacher provides many opportunities for the learner to open up through various activities. The teacher also tries to motivate them to express themselves and give moral support to develop confidence. This activity leads to good relations. The learner asks for solutions for future problems, like improving employability skills or preparing for the

interview, etc.; the language teacher becomes the counselor.

- **Demonstrator:** “Good teaching is one-fourth preparation and three-fourths theater.” This line is attributed to Gail Godwin, an American novelist, and short-story writer. A demonstrator crosses boundaries and goes to the limit to ensure the students have a meaningful experience. When a teacher demonstrates the concepts and ideas, the learning is more effective. The language teacher is the demonstrator of communication skills. Ex. When he teaches pronunciation under speaking skills with the help of the computer, the learner may face the problem of understanding the proper place of the articulation of the word. He takes the help of the teacher. The teacher demonstrates the particular word.
- **Advisor:** the role of a teacher as an advisor is most important in the context of communication skills. The language lab sessions are just the introduction of the activities for the learner to improve their communication skills. Practically, the learner spends a few hours in the language lab. The lab activities only help the learner to know things. If the learner expects a good outcome, he has to do many more things, and it requires the advice of the language teacher. Ex. The teacher advises the learners to listen to the English news the understanding the pronunciations. He asks the learners to create a group of members who wants to improve their communication skills and interact with them only in the target language. In this regard, the language teacher is the advisor.
- **Innovator:** The teacher is the greatest innovator in the world. The teacher keeps a close eye on the students' improvement in communication skills. Whenever he finds that the students face a problem in understanding and improvements are hampered, he introduces the same

activity with innovative thoughts. Ex. Installing the language lab software, the users access in-billed study materials. Every software has its standards. Sometimes the learners need help understanding. The language teacher innovates new activities which help to achieve the target, which is the improvement of the understanding of the learner. Therefore, the teacher plays the role of an innovator.

- **Involver:** Benjamin Franklin says, "Tell me, and I forget. Teach me, and I remember. Involve me, and I learn." Therefore, the success of the learning depends on the learner's active involvement. The teacher expects the devotional involvement of the learners in the laboratory activities with the purpose to stand the learner on any platform of their life. Interest creates active involvement. The language teacher tries to introduce an activity that interests the learners. Ex. The teacher plans for the group discussion to develop speaking skills in the lab. If he decides on the topic for group discussion, the chances are less to involve all the students. The teacher has to motivate them the participation. If the teacher asks them the topic of their choice, they actively participate because it interests them. Therefore, the teacher plays the role of involver in the teaching-learning process. Learners provide the topic of their interest.

- **Informer:** Performing practical communication skills needs information. The teacher acts as a knower in front of the learners. He provides all minute and detailed information. Ex. The teacher plans for the letter-writing activity. He provides information about the points that must be added to the letter. He also talks about the format of the letter.

Conclusion:

Many technological developments are happening in all fields. Education is no exception. Well-equipped computer-based

language laboratories exist in the colleges, but the importance of the teachers must be recognized. Bill Gates says, "Technology is just a tool. The teacher is the most important in terms of getting the kids working together and motivating them." Teacher plays a very important role in the life of learners. During the practice in the language laboratory, a language teacher has a multi-dimensional responsibility. He plays roles like leader, planner, instructor, executor, evaluator, facilitator, communicator, problem solver, motivator, diagnostician, educator, learning resource, demonstrator, advisor, innovator, involver, informer, and many more. The purpose of all the roles is the better teaching-learning process. The ultimate goal of the teaching-learning process is the overall development of the learner.

Limitations and future scope of the study:

In this study, the researcher gathered information from various sources like websites, books, journals, edited books, and many more. Casual interaction with the faculty members of Gaya College of Engineering, Gaya, was also held. The researcher contacted only a few faculty members of other colleges who teach communication skills and use the language lab. He has just interacted with the engineering faculties rather than the faculties who are teaching in other streams like arts, commerce, science, pharmacy, etc. This research only focuses on the role of a language teacher who conducts practical communication skills. For future studies, the researcher may take the help of other colleges and other streams. The researcher may include other subject teachers who conduct practicals in their respective departments.

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